

A Review on Time and Cost Issues of Infrastructure Projects

Anjay Kumar Mishra¹, NK Singh²

Institute of Business Management, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24321/2456.9925.201807>

Abstract

The research is a review research conducted on the issues of time and cost performance of infrastructure projects in global and local context using content analysis. Time extension is a serious issue and further research for specific project should be conducted to search the effective measures in the area. During project based study the quality part should be assured as time and cost may be affected by or can affect quality of the project. The review has highlighted several factors affecting time overrun and cost overrun along with the relation between the same. Time, Cost and Quality are three sides of a project performance triangle. Project is one time unique process with specific objective which is source of innovation and development. Time extension is not an exception but norms for infrastructure projects should be verified through ecological testing and possible measures should be strongly enforced for systematic performance improvements of projects. The study will be significant for policy maker and professional project managers working in the sector of infrastructure development projects.

Keywords: Time, Cost, Issue, Factor, Relationship

Introduction

Nepal is a developing country where around 83% of Nepalese people live in rural areas (CBS, 2012). Agriculture is a major sector of Nepalese economy providing employment opportunity to 66 % of the total population and covering 36 % of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (MoAD, 2013). The very limited participation of rural population in the country's economic growth process is due to the lack of access to basic social and economic facilities. This situation can be improved by providing reliable physical access to social services and technological advancement. In addition, provision of markets to agricultural products with respect to growing demand would ensure increased economic activities.

Development of transportation sector is the backbone of developing rural area of Nepal. It is almost impossible to implement even small development projects in water supply and sanitation, irrigation, hydropower and electrification, building and housing and telecommunication sectors without having transportation infrastructures developed. However, mountainous and steep topography in around 80% of the area of Nepal and diverse geological conditions have

increased more difficulties in developing transportation facilities. Moreover, presence of more than 6000 rivers and streams has demanded construction of large number of motorable bridges to provide all weather access to rural people. This condition has increased the importance of constructing motorable bridges in rural infrastructure development. In this respect, we have to develop many projects with high performance.

Project performance has long been a problem in Nepal. It has been reflected in certain serious time and cost overrun along with accidents in the past. There are numerous accidents that had arisen out of poor quality in bridge construction but could not be reported. The quality issue in Nepal though exists generally, great expenditures of time and resources are wasted each year because of inefficient or non-existent quality management system.

Under DoLIDAR, at present condition, bridges are constructed through different programmes and projects like, Local Road Bridge Programme (LRBP) funded by GoN, the project for Improvement of Community Access in Nepal (CAIP) funded by Government of Japan, Rural Reconstruction and Rehabilitation Sector Development

E-mail Id: anjay_mishra2000@gmail.com

How to cite this article: Mishra AK. A Review on Time and Cost Issues of Infrastructure Projects. *J Adv Res Const Urban Arch* 2018; 3(1&2): 32-46.

Copyright (c) 2018 Journal of Advanced Research in Construction and Urban Architecture (ISSN: 2456-9925)

Programme (RRRSDP) funded by Asian Development Bank, Decentralized Rural Infrastructure and Livelihood Programme (DRILP), funded by Asian Development Bank, Rural Transport Infrastructure Sector Wide Programme (RTISWAP), 30% contribution by the respective DDDC's and 70% by the central government and Rural Accessibility Improvement and Decentralization Project (RAIDP) funded by World Bank in different districts. Local Road Bridge Support Unit through SDC will provide technical support to the bridges financially supported by GON as well as to the bridges supported by various donor agencies. Al together there are more than 200 bridges in under construction and design phase in Local Road Network and in fiscal year 2014/2015 DoLIDAR has carried a walkover survey of 69 bridges throughout the country (DoLIDAR, 2014).

Construction is a very important phase of project life cycle where actual implementation of the project is started. Most of ongoing projects in Nepal, whether they are donor funded or not, are being delayed mostly due to various issues of project management, project administration, contract management, safeguards and multi-dimensional interests of stakeholders etc. The situation has become so harsh that we have no construction projects at national level which has been completed on time without any delay at the specified cost. Also, most of the projects in the national level are having significant cost overruns.

The following currently running national level projects in different sector are discussed to know about their delay and overrun scenario of construction.

Melamchi Water Supply Project

Melamchi water supply project located at Sindhupalchowk was designed to supply 170 million litres per day (MLD) water to the Kathmandu Valley. The construction of the project was started on August 2009 and original completion date was September 2013. The project cost has been doubled and the completion date is estimated to be December, 2015. Physical progress of the project is 45% up to July, 2014 (MWSP, 2014).

Chameliya Hydropower Project

Chameliya hydropower project located at Darchula was designed to produce 30Mega Watt (MW) power. Original completion date was December 2011 but there is 88% physical progress till July, 2014. The project is expected to be completed on March 2015 with additional fund NRs. 1.2 billion (NEA, 2014).

PhalameGaunda Bridge Project

The PhalameGaunda Bridge in Rukum was implemented by Department of Local Infrastructure Development and Agricultural Roads (DoLIDAR). A 45m steel truss bridge was constructed over SaniVeririver conCSJMuting Shyalpakha and Baphikot. The estimated completion date of the project was May 2012 and only 85% of the construction works has

been completed till July, 2014 (DoLIDAR, 2014).

Man River Bridge Project

Man River Bridge in Banke conCSJMuting Paraspur and Gaughtat of the district was implemented by DoLIDAR. This is a reinforced concrete t-beam bridge with well foundation having 96m span. The original completion date of the bridge was July 2013 and only 75% of the construction works has been completed till September, 2014 (DoLIDAR, 2014).

BP Highway Project

BP Highway (Banepa - Sindhuli- Bardibas road) is a national highway having 158 Km. total length connecting Kavre, Sindhuli and Mahottari districts. The construction works was started on November 1996 and it is still ongoing in Khurkot – Nepalthok section (32 Km.). Estimated completion of this project will be on June 2015 with revised cost of NRs 21 billion (DoR, 2013).

Statement of Problem

In Nepalese construction industry, construction projects are being implemented without proper monitoring of proposed plans and schedules incurring time overruns in the projects. Due to various influencing factors of internal and external project environment, the projects are also having significant amount of cost overruns. The influencing factors may include low morale of the concerned people and authorities to the project, contracting party's inability to perform work as per the contract document, paying less attention to the management issues of every project, political liquidity, Government's inability to control its authorities (the ministries and departments) and lack of coordination between contracting parties and government agencies. Moreover, interdependence of time and cost of the projects has increased, being influenced by the complex project environment. This has again resulted to the increase in complexity of construction projects. There are hardly any projects without time and cost overrun in local, regional and national level. (MWSP, 2013, NEA, 2012, DoLIDAR, 2013, DoR, 2013).

Research Objective

The objective of the paper is to review the issues of time and cost performance of infrastructure projects.

Methodology

This paper is a review paper where global, regional and local papers have been reviewed using content analysis for infrastructure projects. Legal provisions and Practices have been reviewed. This paper will be guiding paper for further digging research in the Area to analyse the time and cost issue along with relation between time and cost on the basis of project performance.

Result and Discussion

Construction industry has become an important player in the economy of many countries, especially in developing

countries. This industry contributes to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment rate of many nations and for this reason it is considered vital for the economic development of any nation. Moreover, it can also be affirmed that construction activities have become a significant market due to the fact that this industry procures products and material from other businesses in other sectors (Arcila, 2012).

Construction industry is always known as very complex, versatile and fragmented industry. Due to its nature, it always is faced by serious problems. One of the most significant problems in this industry is construction delay. Various studies have been conducted on identifying the causes of delay, however very less attention has been paid on its effects (Memon et al., 2010).

The inability to complete projects on time and within budget continues to be a chronic problem worldwide and is worsening (Ahmed et al., 2003). Cost and time overruns have been common problems in every construction project worldwide. Numerous factors such as utility and weather damage delays can cause the costs of construction to exceed the budget and extend project schedule. Understanding the specific causes of cost and time overruns due to design or changed conditions can help control cost and time extension on projects (Vidalis and Najafi, 2002).

Construction industry is highly dynamic sector and plays very important role in the development of country and hence in Malaysia, construction industry started a rapid growth since its independence. However, construction industry in Malaysia is facing chronic problems including poor performance of time and cost, construction waste, poor productivity and over dependent of foreign workers. Of these challenges, poor time and cost performance is considered as a critical issue. (Memon et al., 2012). According to Sambasivan and Soon, the sector accounted for nearly 3.3% of GDP in the year 2005 and employed about 600,000 workers including 109,000 foreign workers. The huge volume and complexity of projects in Malaysia's construction sector pose a great challenge and provide a wealth of opportunities to various companies in the construction industry (Sambasivan and Soon, 2006).

In Palestine, the construction industry is one of the main economic driving sectors, supporting the economy. It contributes to 26% of the Palestinian GDP. It also plays a basic role in providing homes, public facilities and infrastructure, absorbing work forces and in improving the West Bank economy as a whole. However, many local construction projects report poor performance in cost and time due to causes that include: unavailability of materials, frequent amendments of design and drawings, poor coordination among participants, ineffective monitoring and feedback, lack of project leadership skills (Mahamid and Amund, 2012).

In the construction industry, the aim of project control is

to ensure that projects finish on time, within the allocated budget and achieve other project objectives. A successful project is the only project which has accomplished its technical performance, maintained its schedule, and remained within budgeted costs. Project management tools and techniques play an important role in the effective management of a project. Construction time and cost are fundamental considerations in project management and regarded as most important parameters for measuring success of any project. Poor performance of time and cost can lead to a significant amount of time and cost overrun which is global phenomenon (Memon et al., 2012).

Time and Cost Overrun

Many researchers have defined time and cost overruns in their literatures. According to Azhar&Faroouqi, 2008, late completion of works as compared to the planned schedule or contract schedule is known as delay. Delay occurs when the progress of a contract falls behind its scheduled program. It may be caused by any party to the contract and may be a direct result of one or more circumstances. A contract delay has adverse effects on both the owner and contractor (either in the form of lost revenues or extra expenses) and it often raises the contentious issue of delay responsibility, which may result in conflicts that frequently reach the courts. A cost overrun occurs when the final cost of the project exceeds the original estimates (Azhar & Faroouqi, 2008).

According to Memonet al., 2010, time overrun can be refereed as effect of construction delay. A delay in construction industry is defined as lack of progress compared to baseline construction schedule. Baseline construction schedule refers to the schedule prepared by contractor before the start of the project and approved by the client. Construction delays is an event resulting in work activity starting, or project completion, later than originally planned or an interruption or a hindrance to a planned program.

But, according to Assaf& Al-Hejji, 2006, Construction delay refers to the time overrun in completion or delivery of project beyond the data on which parties agreed or project completion data specified. Failure to achieve targeted time, budgeted cost and specified quality result in various unexpected negative effects on the projects. Normally, when the projects are delayed, they are either extended or accelerated and therefore, incur additional cost. The normal practices usually allow a percentage of the project cost as a contingency allowance in the contract price and this allowance is usually based on judgment. Although the contract parties agreed upon the extra time and cost associated with delay, in many cases there were problems between the owner and contractor as to whether the contractor was entitled to claim the extra cost. Such situations, usually involved questioning the facts, causal factors and contract interpretation. Therefore, delays in construction projects give

rise to dissatisfaction to all the parties involved and the main role of the project manager is to make sure that the projects are completed within the budgeted time and cost. Time overrun can simply be expressed by the following equation.

$$\text{Time Overrun} = \frac{\text{Actual Construction Duration} - \text{Original Construction Duration}}{\text{Original Construction Duration}} \times 100\%$$

When an infrastructure project is planned, the sponsoring department prepares estimates of time and funds (cost) needed to complete the project. An expected date of completion is also announced. The actual date of completion is invariably different from the expected date. We define 'time overrun' as the time difference between the actual and the initially planned (i.e., expected) dates of completion. We measure the time difference in months. A related term used in the paper is the 'implementation phase'. It is defined as the duration in which a project is planned to be completed, i.e., the duration between the date of approval of the project and its expected date of completion. Therefore, for each project we can define percentage time overrun as the ratio of the time overrun and the implementation phase for the project. Similarly, we define 'cost overrun' as the difference between the actual cost and the initially projected (i.e., expected) cost of the projects. The actual costs become known only at the time of completion, the projected costs are the estimated costs when a project is planned. Percentage cost overrun for a project is defined as the ratio of the cost overrun and the initially anticipated cost of the project (Singh, 2009).

On the other hand, Ameh and Osegbo, 2011, states that time overrun is the extension of time beyond planned completion dates usually traceable to contractors. They defined time overrun as the time lapse between the agreed estimation or completion date and the actual date of completion. Time overrun can be understood as the time during which some part of construction project is completed beyond the project completion date or not performed as planned due to an unanticipated circumstance (Ameh and Osegbo, 2011).

Many researchers have also defined cost overrun in their literatures. According to Nyabwari, N. E., 2012, cost overrun is defined as excess of actual cost over budget. Cost overrun is also sometimes called cost escalation, cost increase or budget overrun. Cost overrun can also be defined as the change in contract amount divided by the original contract award amount.

Cost overrun can simply be represented by the following equation.

$$\text{Cost Overrun} = \frac{\text{Total Payment Amount} - \text{Original Contract Amount}}{\text{Original Contract Amount}} \times 100\%$$

So, cost overruns can be defined as the difference between the original cost estimate of project and actual construction cost on completion of works of a commercial sector construction project (Nyabwari, 2012).

Distinction between Delay and Time Overrun

Delay and time overruns are very similar terms frequently used to represent the lack of progress in construction industry replacing each other, but there is a slight distinction between them. Delay refers to lack of project progress within the baseline construction schedule as compared to it, whereas time overrun is any delay beyond the baseline construction schedule. Time overrun itself is the most important effect of construction delay, which is followed by cost overrun. According to Aibinu and Jagboro, 2002, delay is a situation when the contractor and the project owner jointly or severally contribute to the non-completion of the project within the original or the stipulated or agreed contract period.

Delays occur in most construction projects, either simple or complex. In construction, delay can be defined as the extension of time in the completion of project. In short delay means failure to complete project in targeted time & budgeted cost as agreed in contract. The occurrence of delay may concurrently with other delays and all of them can impact the project completion date. When the project completion date is exceeded, the amount of time by which the project completion date is exceeded is known as time overrun of the project (Salunkhe and Patil, 2014).

Issues of Time and Cost Overrun

Global Issues

The Libyan construction industry contributes less to the country's economy than do manufacturing or other services industries. Officially, construction accounted for only 2.1 % of the annual gross domestic product (GDP). However, the growth influenced the country's economic development. As defined by Hillebrandt, 1985, in developed countries, construction is considered unique in that it can stimulate the growth of other industrial sectors. Hence to consider growth of the construction industry in terms of its contribution to GDP in isolation is somewhat misleading that is, to do so understates the crucial role played by construction. Therefore, improving construction efficiency by means of cost effectiveness and timeliness would certainly contribute to cost saving for the country as a whole. Effort directed to cost and time effectiveness were associated with managing time and cost, which in this study was approached via investigating causes of delay at construction projects in Libya. Like other developing countries, such as Nigeria, Saudi Arabia and Malaysia, Libya suffers construction time and cost overruns (Tumi et al., 2009).

The debate in the construction industry on how to minimize or eliminate delays and cost overruns has been on for some time among professionals, clients and/or end users, and the policy makers. The funding for construction industry activities is, in many countries, used to regulate the economy. As the construction industry continues to grow in size, so do planning and budgeting problems. This is

because it is common for projects not to be completed on time and within the initial project budget. There are quite a number of examples at the national and internal scene. For instance, most of the construction projects in Uganda have had problems with delay in completion and cost overruns and this has caused a lot of concern. A local example is the Northern by-pass in Kampala which was to take two and a half years instead took more than 5 years and the cost had similarly gone up by more than 100 %. Because of construction delays and cost overruns, less and less work is performed despite the increase in construction budgets (Apolot et al., 2010).

Florida Department of Transportation (FDOT) of the US conducted a research to identify the reasons why it has experienced cost and time overruns in transportation projects. An examination of 708 recently completed projects that had experienced cost and time overruns was conducted. Contract costs, time durations, and the causes of delays were taken from these various projects from the FDOT within the fiscal years from 1999 to 2001. Highway construction projects from FDOT were focused on completed highway construction projects such as roadway construction, roadway rehabilitation, bridge construction, etc. The original contract amount for these projects over the two years exceeded \$1.9 billion. The cost overrun exceeded \$200 million over the original contract amount. The original contract over the same period of time was about 200 thousand days and the time overrun were 17% of the original contract time. Furthermore, it was found that during year 1996/1997 about two-thirds of the overruns (\$65 million of \$104 million) of FDOT projects were attributed from design errors and omissions. Design errors and omissions were found to be the leading cause of delay in cost and time overruns. In addition, design errors and changed conditions were also influential external factors causing cost and time overruns during two years period from 1999 to 2001. Furthermore, consultants shared more than half of the delays in the FDOT highway construction projects compared to FDOT staff, and third parties. The FDOT highway construction data provided useful information on cost and time overruns (Vidalis and Najafi, 2002).

According to Aibinu and Jagboro, 2002, the Nigerian construction industry continues to occupy an important position in the nation's economy even though it contributes less than the manufacturing or other service industries. The contribution of the construction industry to national economic growth CSJMUessitates improved efficiency in the industry by means of cost-effectiveness and timelines and would certainly contribute to cost savings for the country as a whole. A major criticism facing the Nigerian construction industry is the growing rate of delays in project delivery (Aibinu and Jagboro, 2002).

In a series of empirical studies covering twenty countries

across the five continents, Flyvbjerg et al (2002, 2003, and 2004) have shown that infrastructure projects often suffer from cost overruns. The authors have studied 258 large infrastructure projects from 20 countries including developed as well as developing countries. They have shown that ninety percent of large transport projects suffer from cost overrun (Flyvbjerg et al., 2004).

In Nigeria, Ajanlekoko observed that the performance of the construction industry in terms of time was poor. Odeyinka and Yusif have shown that seven out of ten projects surveyed in Nigeria suffered delays in their execution.

Asian Issues

A study was carried out to investigate the statistical relationship between actual and estimated cost of road construction projects using data from road construction projects awarded in the West Bank in Palestine over the years 2004 to 2008. The findings reveal that all projects suffer from cost deviation, it is found that 76% of projects have cost under-estimates and 24% have cost over-estimates. The deviation between estimated and actual cost has an average of 14.6%, ranging from 39.3% to 98%. These results agree with previous studies in that the cost deviation is predominant in road construction projects. The results show that cost under-estimates are more common than cost over-estimates in road construction projects implemented in the West Bank regardless the project category. Regression models that relate cost deviation in road construction projects and project size (i.e. road length and road width) reveal a very weak relationship. (Mahamid and Bruland, 2012)

In Saudi Arabia, Assaf and Al-Hejji found that only 30% of construction projects were completed within the scheduled completion dates and that the average time overrun was between 10% and 30%. Ogunlana and Promkuntong conducted a study on construction delays in Thailand. Chan and Kumaraswamy studied delays in Hong Kong construction industry. They emphasized that timely delivery of projects within budget and to the level of quality standard specified by the client is an index of successful project delivery. The construction sector in Malaysia, a fast developing country in South-East Asia has not escaped the problem of delays. In 2005, about 17.3% (of 417 government contract projects in Malaysia) were found to be delayed by more than 3 months or abandoned (Sambasivan and Soon, 2006).

South Asian issues

Infrastructure projects in India are infamous for delays and cost overruns. Even the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MOSPI) confirms that many projects are suffering from delays and cost overruns. For several reasons delays and cost overruns have implications significant from economic and political points of view. For one, in most cases, these projects are funded by taxpayers' money.

Therefore, people should know how efficiently their money is utilized by officials while making provisions of public goods and services. Two, delays in project implementation mean that the people and the economy have to wait for infrastructure facilities longer than is CSJM Uessary. This in turn limits the growth potential of the economy at large. Three, services provided by infrastructure projects serve as input for many other sectors of the economy. Therefore, cost overruns lead to an increase in the capital-output-ratio for the entire economy. In simple words, delays and cost overruns reduce the efficiency of available resources and limit the growth potential of the entire economy (Ram Singh, 2009).

In Pakistan, construction sector is an important sector although not working to its fullest potential but still of prime significance to the country. Growth in this sector is critical for growth in national income as it is among the largest sectors that generates employment within the country as well as a key driver for economic development of Pakistan. Like many other developing countries, Pakistan is also facing critical project management related issues among which delay and cost overrun are quite prominent. There are several factors that are responsible for delays and cost overruns. Many researches and studies have been conducted to find the causes of delays and cost overrun, but it seems there lots of things have to be done to improve the scenario (Azharand Farouqi, 2008).

S. P. Baral conducted a study to outline the effects of delays in smaller construction projects under Town Development Fund (TDF) of Nepal in the year 2003. The results showed that 20% of the studied projects were completed before the scheduled completion date, 20% projects were completed on time and remaining 60% projects were found to be delayed. The study was conducted by taking samples from School building construction projects.

Causes of Time and Cost Overrun

A study was conducted to investigate the causes of delays and cost overruns in construction projects in Uganda's public sector. The five most important causes of delays and cost overrun were found to be changes in scope, delayed payment to contractor, poor monitoring and control and high inflation and interest rates. These results were also validated by the cases from Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) which indeed showed that these are the most important factors. Stakeholders in the construction industry are advised to minimize change in scope of work as it has the most effect on cost and time overrun. It is recommended that there should be improvement in project management; change from the traditional contract type to the design-build type; and improved cash flow on the part of the client so as to reduce payment delays. The results of this research should help construction practitioners, policy makers and researchers in the field of construction management (Apolot et al., 2010).

Sambasivan and Soon, 2006 investigated the causes and effects of delays facing in the Malaysian construction industry. A questionnaire was designed and distributed among the three major groups of participants (clients, consultants and contractors). They identified main causes of delay and ten most important causes were: (1) contractor's improper planning, (2) contractor's poor site management, (3) inadequate contractor experience, (4) inadequate client's finance and payments for completed work, (5) problems with subcontractors, (6) shortage in material, (7) labor supply, (8) equipment availability and failure, (9) lack of communication between parties, and (10) mistakes during the construction stage. Again, they also identified main effects of delay and they were: (1) time overrun, (2) cost overrun, (3) disputes, (4) arbitration, (5) litigation, and (6) total abandonment. As an important contribution, they also studied the empirical relationships between the causes and effects of delays. They isolated the causes of delay for each of the six effects. They believed that the results of this study can be of immense help to the practitioners (clients, contractors and consultants) and academicians. The practitioners can better understand the dynamics of project management and make efforts to reduce the incidences of delays. The academicians can conduct similar studies in other parts of world and identify causes and effects of delays. As mentioned earlier, some causes and effects may be unique to certain countries (Sambasivan and Soon, 2006).

Vidalis and Najafi, 2002 conducted a research to investigate the factors causing cost and time overrun which were found to be plans modifications, changed conditions, lack of project coordination, and design related problems. The overview of past highway construction projects in Florida provide useful information on how to reduce delays in highway construction projects. From the analysis of over 700 FDOT (Florida Department of Transportation) projects, it was found that the majority of cost and time overruns were due to design factors, changed conditions, and designer errors and omissions by the consultants. The study results indicate that contractors and DOTs should carefully examine each construction contract carefully to minimize delays. Specific emphasis should be given to the design phase. Cost and time overruns in construction projects cannot realistically be eliminated. However, DOT's could take several steps such as reviewing design plans prior to construction. Furthermore, they should closely look at contractors' performance and conduct additional preliminary research and investigation on-site before bidding. The implication of other innovative contracting techniques such incentive/ decenter, lane rental, and A + B contracting should reduce cost and time overruns (Vidalis and Najafi, 2002).

In another study carried out in Turkey, the main survey of project management consultants, contractors and owners / clients as discussed in this article relates to the construction

of residential projects in Turkey. The survey focused on identifying and ranking in order of importance, the main factors causing cost overruns. 40 sub-factors have been identified under 5 groups, which are macroeconomic, workforce, project finance, project management and other external factors. The main conclusions of the survey were as follows.

The overall ranking results indicate that the three groups felt that the most significant factors that can cause excessive residential projects cost overruns in Turkey are improper planning, inaccurate project cost estimation, high cost of needed resources (money, men, materials and machinery), lack of skilled workforce, price of construction materials and high land prices.

Other sub-factors that emerged clearly as not very important, but of interest, are lack of coordination, cost of the reworks, inadequate duration of contract period, lack of communication between parties and poor on-site management.

The results show that most of the problems in residential construction projects are originated from poor resource management (human, technical and material). These causes should be controlled right away from the planning to the implementation and management stages. Good practice in planning, coordinating, controlling and monitoring procedures is therefore has to be recognized.

In conclusion, it is believed that by focusing on the relative levels of impact of the identified sub-factors, the project team/ owners could be guided well in their efforts to addressing the factors in a cost-effective manner (Durdyev et al., 2012).

An another study was conducted to investigate the factors affecting time overrun in road construction projects in the West Bank in Palestine in order to identify these factors and their frequency of occurrence from contractors' viewpoint. 52 factors affecting time overrun were identified through detailed literature review. The identified factors are combined into eight groups. The field survey included 34 contractors. The top ten frequent factors affecting time overrun as seen from the contractors' viewpoint were found to be the following. (1) segmentation of the West Bank and limited movement between areas, (2) political situation, (3) progress payments delay by owner, (4) lack of equipment efficiency, (5) difficulties in financing project by contractor, (6) personal conflicts among labors, (7) poor communication by consultant with other construction parties, (8) conflict between contractor and other parties, (9) award project to lowest bid price and (10) unreasonable project time frame by the owner (Mahamid, 2013).

In an another study conducted in 2011 by Ameh and Osegbo, it was established that among the various factors that causes time overrun, inadequate fund for the project, inadequate planning of project before take-off, inadequate tools and

equipment, delay in delivery of materials, subcontractors' incompetency and design changes during project execution top the list. Adequate funding guarantees reasonable cash flow while good planning ensures uninterrupted progress of work and these are basic ingredients for the realization of key objectives of any project. The project owner and project manager should keep their eyes on these key factors during project execution as these factors could result in reasonable time overrun on projects (Ameh and Osegbo, 2011).

Effects of Time and Cost Overrun

A study conducted by Aibinu and Jagboro, (2002) revealed six effects of delay on project delivery in Nigerian construction industry which were: time overrun, cost overrun, dispute, arbitration, total abandonment and litigation. Similarly, Sambasivan and Soon (2006) disclosed the same effects of delay in Malaysian construction industry. Haseeb et al (2011) identified effects of delays in Pakistan construction industry as clash, claims, total desertion and slowing down the growth of the construction sector. Ramabodu and Verster (2010) identified critical factors that cause cost overruns in construction projects as changes in scope of work on site, incomplete design at the time of tender, contractual claims (extension of time with cost), lack of cost planning and monitoring of funds, delays in costing variations and additional works. Chileshe and Berko (2010) indicated that causes cost overrun in Ghanaian road construction sector were delay in monthly payments to contractors; variations; inflation, and schedule slippage. Again, these explain the causes of delays and the effect of cost overrun. According to Ahmed et al., 2003, delay and cost overruns are a phenomenon in construction projects and have a negative effect on clients, contractors, and consultants in terms of growth in adversarial relationships, mistrust, litigation, arbitration and a general feeling of trepidation towards each other.

In a study conducted by Kikwasi to investigate the causes and effects of delays and disruptions in construction projects in Tanzania in 2012, fourteen important effects of delays were identified and ranked. They, in rank order are as follows. (1) Time overrun, (2) Cost overrun, (3) Negative social impact, (4) Idling resources, (5) Disputes, (6) Arbitration, (7) Delaying by the client to return the loans, (8) Poor quality of work due to hurry, (9) Delaying in getting profit by clients, (10) Bankruptcy, (11) Litigation, (12) Create stress on contractors, (13) Total abandonment and (14) Acceleration losses (Kikwasi, 2012).

Several factors cause the overall delay in the construction project such as some within contractor's liability and some are within owner's liability. It is hard to distinguish due to overlapping nature of the events that which party or parties are responsible and what ingredients of the delay cause. It is mostly seen that delay problems are cause of dispute, negotiation, lawsuit, total desertion, litigation

and abandonment. We can say that the parties included in contract through claims agree on the additional capital and extra time linked with construction delay. The consequences of delay are different for different parties. The general consequences are the loss of wealth, time and capacity. For owner, delay means the loss of income and unavailability of facilities. For contractor, delay means the loss of money for extra spending on equipment and materials and hiring the labor and loss of time (Haseeb et al., 2011).

In a study conducted by NE Nyabwari in 2009 to investigate the causes and effects of cost overrun in civil works projects in Kenya, the following effects of cost overrun in ranked order were identified; Delay, Supplementary agreement, Additional cost, budget short fall, Adversarial relationship between participants of the project, Loss of reputation to the consultant, the consultant will be viewed as incompetent by project owners, High cost of supervision and contract administration for consultants, Delayed payments to contractors, The contractor will suffer from budget short fall of the client, Poor quality, Dissatisfaction by project owners and consequently by end users, Negative attitude towards the construction industry by the higher public authority and by the society as a whole, The contribution of the construction industry to the growth of national economy of the country will be less, Cost overruns in construction projects prevent the planned increase in property and service production from taking place, and this phenomenon in turn affects, in a negative way, the rate of national growth. Weakens the growth of the construction industry by eroding mutual trust and respect, Pours money uncessarily to the project at hand at the expense of other new projects, Distorts fair and equitable resource distribution, Discourage investment, the investment on building construction by public clients will be less, hence the number of projects will decrease in the future, Creates skeptical outlook on appraisal of other new construction projects, Some project owners (clients) become reluctant to effect additional payments to contractors and they view the cost overrun as a fabricated thing. This will propel to delay the project and become a source of dispute among participants of the project, Creates frustration on stakeholders.

F. Nega in 2009 conducted a similar study to investigate about the causes and effects of cost overrun in public building construction projects in Ethiopia and found the similar effects as stated above.

Remedial Measures to Control Time and Cost Overrun

Sambasivan and Soon, 2006, investigated the causes and effects of delays and has prepared a set of prescriptions to reduce delays. They divided the prescriptions to be adopted into three groups: (1) prescriptions for the clients, (2) prescriptions for the consultants, and (3) prescriptions for the contractors.

Prescriptions for the clients: (1) while selecting the contractors, clients have to make sure that the contractors are not selected based only on the lowest bid. The selected contractor must have sufficient experience, technical capability, financial capability, and sufficient manpower to execute the project, (2) clients should not interfere frequently during the execution and keep making major changes to the requirements. This can cause inordinate delays in the project, (3) clients should have the finances in time to pay the contractors after completion of a work. Therefore, clients should work closely with the financing bodies and institutions to release the payment on schedule, and (4) clients must make quick decisions to solve any problem that arise during the execution.

Prescriptions for the consultants: (1) While drawing the contract between the client and contractor, the consultant must include items such as duration of contract, mechanism to solve disputes, mechanism to assess the causes of delay, if there are any and risk management plans, (2) consultants should prepare and approve drawings on time, and (3) consultants should monitor the work closely by making inspections at appropriate times.

Prescriptions for the contractors: (1) Contractors should not take up the job in which they do not have sufficient expertise, (2) contractors should have able site-managers for the smooth execution of work, (3) contractors must plan their work properly and provide the entire schedule to the clients, and (4) contractors must make sure they have a sound financial backing (Sambasivan and Soon, 2006).

Memon et al., 2012 conducted a study to evaluate time and cost performance in infrastructure projects in Malaysia and suggested mitigation measures to improve time and cost performance. The following measures were suggested to improve time performance: (1) Proper planning work, (2) Committed leadership and management, (3) Send clear and complete message to worker to ensure effective communication, (4) Hire skilled workers to achieve good progress, avoid poor quality of work, more rectification and double handling, (5) Close monitoring, (6) Training and development of all participant to support delivery process, (7) Focus on the quality, cost and delivery of the project, (8) Use new construction technologies (IBS-Industrialize Building System), (9) Adoption of tools and techniques i.e.: Value Management, Lean Thinking, Total Quality Management, (10) Provide knowledge/ training to unskilled workers based on their scope of work, (11) Fully utilize the construction team, (12) Focus on client's need and (13) Measure performance against other projects.

Memon et al., 2012 suggested the following mitigation measures to improve cost performance: (1) Effective strategic planning, (2) Proper project planning and scheduling, (3) Effective Site management and supervision, (4) Frequent progress meeting, (5) Proper emphasis on past experience, (6) Use of experienced subcontractors

and suppliers, (7) Use of appropriate construction methods, (8) Use up to date technology utilization, (9) Clear information and communication channels, (10) Frequent coordination between the parties, (11) Perform a preconstruction planning of project tasks and resources needs, (12) Developing human resources in the construction industry, (13) Comprehensive contract administration, (14) Systematic control mechanism and (15) Improving contract award procedure by giving less weight to prices and more weight to the capabilities and past performance of contractors (Memon et al., 2012).

Project Time – Cost Relationship

There are two classifications of costs associated with construction projects, direct costs and indirect costs. Direct costs include the labor, material and equipment operating costs necessary to put work in place. Indirect costs include supervision, job and home office overhead, profit, financing, and the cost of inflation. Direct costs can be allocated to each activity on the project. Indirect costs, on the other hand, cannot be realistically prorated and assigned to each separate activity. Indirect costs add up continuously throughout the duration of the project, and if a Critical Path Method (CPM) or precedence network is used for scheduling, cannot be divided up among activities, some of which have float (Baker, 1991).

Total indirect cost on a project increases with time as shown in the Figure. This relationship is not necessarily linear. The actual shape of the curve depends on the complexity of the project and the types of indirect cost involved. Total indirect cost includes overhead costs, cost of interests and cost for damages and penalties etc. Job overhead and general or home/ office overhead, are significant part of the total indirect costs, which usually increase linearly with time. These costs are normally assumed to be spread out over the entire project with a constant cost per day assigned; however, if all the overhead costs equally throughout the project duration, the curve will not be linear and may have points of discontinuity (Alexander, 2011).

Figure 1. Project Time-Cost Relationship
(Adopted from Shr and Chen, 2006)

Most contractors must borrow money or use credit to finance construction costs. The cost of interest or finance costs increase with project time. This relationship is not always linear, the shape will depend on the type of loan or credit extended and the repayment terms. Periodic loans or credit extensions made throughout the project will result in a curve with points of discontinuity as in previous case.

If the contract specifies liquidated damages or penalties for late completion or bonuses for early completion, the cost of the project as a function of time is affected. Since the bonus is an additional payment to the contractor, it is shown as a “negative cost.” Shapes of penalty and bonus curves may vary, depending on the particular contract provisions. The total direct cost will always decrease as project duration increases, as shown in Figure. Efforts to compress or “crash” activity completion time will result in higher direct cost for each activity (Shr and Chen, 2006).

Once curves for all costs and bonuses or savings are established, they are added together to yield a “Total Project Cost vs. Time” curve such as the one shown in Figure. The lowest point on the curve gives the lowest cost project duration. This duration may not be the “ideal duration.” There may be other considerations within the company, not involving the project, that the project manager must take into consideration when selecting the ideal project duration.

Roles of Parties to Contract According to FIDIC, Multilateral Development Bank (MDB) Harmonized Edition, June-2010

The Employer

According to FIDIC (International Federation for Consulting Engineers) Multilateral Development Bank Harmonized Edition-June 2010, Employer means the person named as Employer in the contract data and the legal successors in title to this person.

The Employer shall give the Contractor right of access to, and possession of, all parts of the Site within the time (or times) stated in the Contract Data. The right and possession may not be exclusive to the Contractor. If, under the Contract, the Employer is required to give (to the Contractor) possession of any foundation, structure, plant or means of access, the Employer shall do so in the time and manner stated in the Specification. However, the Employer may withhold any such right or possession until the Performance Security has been received.

If no such time is stated in the Contract Data, the Employer shall give the Contractor right of access to, and possession of, the Site within such times as required to enable the Contractor to proceed without disruption in accordance with the program submitted. If the Contractor suffers delay and/ or incurs Cost as a result of a failure by the Employer to give any such right or possession within such time, the Contractor shall give notice to the Engineer

and shall be entitled subject to Contractor's Claims to:

- a). An extension of time for any such delay, if completion is or will be delayed, under Clause Extension of Time for Completion,
- b). Payment of any such Cost plus profit, which shall be included in the Contract Price

After receiving this notice, the Engineer shall proceed in accordance with Clause Determinations to agree or determine these matters. However, if and to the extent that the Employer's failure was caused by any error or delay by the Contractor, including an error in, or delay in the submission of, any of the Contractor's Documents, the Contractor shall not be entitled to such extension of time, Cost or profit.

The Engineer

According to FIDIC (Multilateral Development Bank Harmonized Edition, June 2010), the Engineer means the person appointed by the Employer to act as the Engineer for the purposes of the Contract and named in the Contract Data, or other person appointed from time to time by the Employer and notified to the Contractor under Clause Replacement of the Engineer.

The Employer shall appoint the Engineer who shall carry out the duties assigned to him in the Contract. The Engineer's staff shall include suitably qualified engineers and other professionals who are competent to carry out these duties.

The Engineer shall have no authority to amend the Contract. The Engineer may exercise the authority attributable to the Engineer as specified in or CSJMUessarily to be implied from the Contract. If the Engineer is required to obtain the approval of the Employer before exercising a specified authority, the requirements shall be as stated in the Particular Conditions. The Employer shall promptly inform the Contractor of any change to the authority attributed to the Engineer.

However, whenever the Engineer exercises a specified authority for which the Employer's approval is required, then (for the purposes of the Contract) the Employer shall be deemed to have given approval.

Except as Otherwise Stated in these Conditions

- a). Whenever carrying out duties or exercising authority, specified in or implied by the Contract, the Engineer shall be deemed to act for the Employer
- b). The Engineer has no authority to relieve either Party of any duties, obligations or responsibilities under the Contract
- c). Any approval, check, certificate, consent, examination, inspection, instruction, notice, proposal, request, test, or similar act by the Engineer (including absence of disapproval) shall not relieve the Contractor from any responsibility he has under the Contract, including responsibility for errors, omissions, discrepancies and

non-compliances

- d). Any act by the Engineer in response to a Contractor's request except as otherwise expressly specified shall be notified in writing to the Contractor within 28 days of receipt

The Following Provisions Shall Apply

The Engineer shall obtain the specific approval of the Employer before taking action under the following Sub-Clauses of these Conditions:

- a). Sub-Clause 4.12: agreeing or determining an extension of time and/or additional cost
- b). Sub-Clause 13.1: instructing a Variation, except
 - In an emergency situation as determined by the Engineer,
 - If such a Variation would increase the Accepted Contract Amount by less than the percentage specified in the Contract Data
- c). Sub-Clause 13.3: approving a proposal for Variation submitted by the Contractor in accordance with Sub-Clause 13.1 or 13.2
- d). Sub-Clause 13.4: specifying the amount payable in each of the applicable currencies

Notwithstanding the obligation, as set out above, to obtain approval, if, in the opinion of the Engineer, an emergency occurs affecting the safety of life or of the Works or of adjoining property, he may, without relieving the Contractor of any of his duties and responsibility under the Contract, instruct the Contractor to execute all such work or to do all such things as may, in the opinion of the Engineer, be necessary to abate or reduce the risk. The Contractor shall forthwith comply, despite the absence of approval of the Employer, with any such instruction of the Engineer. The Engineer shall determine an addition to the Contract Price, in respect of such instruction, in accordance with Clause 13 and shall notify the Contractor accordingly, with a copy to the Employer.

The Contractor

According to FIDIC (Multilateral Development Bank Harmonized Edition, June 2010), the Contractor means the person(s) named as Contractor in the Letter of Tender accepted by the Employer and the legal successors in title to this person(s).

The Contractor shall design (to the extent specified in the Contract), execute and complete the Works in accordance with the Contract and with the Engineer's instructions, and shall remedy any defects in the Works.

The Contractor shall provide the Plant and Contractor's Documents specified in the Contract, and all Contractor's Personnel, Goods, consumables and other things and services, whether of a temporary or permanent nature, required in and for this design, execution, completion and remedying of defects.

All equipment, material, and services to be incorporated in or required for the Works shall have their origin in any eligible source country as defined by the Bank.

The Contractor shall be responsible for the adequacy, stability and safety of all Site operations and of all methods of construction. Except to the extent specified in the Contract, the Contractor (i) shall be responsible for all Contractor's Documents, Temporary Works, and such design of each item of Plant and Materials as is required for the item to be in accordance with the Contract, and (ii) shall not otherwise be responsible for the design or specification of the Permanent Works.

The Contractor shall, whenever required by the Engineer, submit details of the arrangements and methods which the Contractor proposes to adopt for the execution of the Works. No significant alteration to these arrangements and methods shall be made without this having previously been notified to the Engineer.

If the Contract specifies that the Contractor shall design any part of the Permanent Works, then unless otherwise stated in the Particular Conditions:

- a). The Contractor shall submit to the Engineer the Contractor's Documents for this part in accordance with the procedures specified in the Contract;
- b). These Contractor's Documents shall be in accordance with the Specification and Drawings, shall be written in the language for communications defined in Sub-Clause 1.4 [Law and Language], and shall include additional information required by the Engineer to add to the Drawings for co-ordination of each Party's designs;
- c). The Contractor shall be responsible for this part and it shall, when the Works are completed, be fit for such purposes for which the part is intended as are specified in the Contract; and
- d). Prior to the commencement of the Tests on Completion, the Contractor shall submit to the Engineer the "as-built" documents and, if applicable, operation and maintenance manuals in accordance with the Specification and in sufficient detail for the Employer to operate, maintain, dismantle, reassemble, adjust and repair this part of the Works. Such part shall not be considered to be completed for the purposes of taking-over under Sub-Clause 10.1 [Taking Over of the Works and Sections] until these documents and manuals have been submitted to the Engineer

Provisions Regarding Time and Cost in Relevant Act/ Standard Document

Public Procurement Act and Rules -2007

Clause No. 53: Amendment to Procurement Contract.

"A procurement contract may be amended by written consent of both the parties subject to non-alteration of the basic nature or scope of the work..."

Clause No. 54: Variation Order.

"...if the circumstances that could not be foreseen at the time of signing of procurement contract arise in the course of implementation of the procurement contract, the competent authority may, by stating clear reasons thereof, issue as prescribed, a variation order for a variation of up to fifteen percent and for a variation order above it, a variation order may be issued as per the Government of Nepal, Council of Ministers by complying with the procedures as prescribed..."

Clause No. 55: Price Adjustment in Procurement Contract.

"...if price needs to be adjusted in the course of implementation of a procurement contract having duration exceeding fifteen months the competent authority may adjust price..."

Clause No. 56: Provision Concerning Extension of Contract Period.

"...if the period of a procurement contract is to be inevitably extended due to force majeure, failure of the public entity to make available the materials to be made available by it or other reasonable causes, the competent authority may extend the period on the prescribed grounds..." (PPA, 2007).

The Public Procurement Rules - 2007 (PPR, 2007) gives more clear guidelines to the above clauses.

Condition of Contract for Construction, FIDIC (MDB Harmonized Edition, June-2010)

Clause No. 8.2: Time for Completion.

"...the contractor shall complete the whole of the Works and each Section (if any), within the Time for Completion for the Works or Section..."

Clause No. 8.4: Extension of time for completion.

"...the Contractor shall be entitled to an extension of the Time for Completion if and to the extent that completion is or will be delayed by any of the following causes..."

Clause No. 8.5: Delays caused by authorities.

"... then this delay or disruption will be considered as a cause of delay under Extension of Time for Completion..."

Clause No. 13.1: Right to Vary.

"...variation may be initiated by the Engineer at any time prior to issuing the Taking-Over Certificate for the Works..." (FIDIC, 2010).

Standard Bid Document for Procurement of Works for above 6 million rupees issued by PPMO

Clause No. 27: Extension of the Intended Completion Date.

"...the Project Manager shall extend the Intended Completion Date if a Compensation Event occurs or a Variation is issued which makes it impossible for Completion to be achieved by the Intended Completion Date..."

Clause No. 28: Acceleration.

"...when the Employer wants the Contractor to finish before the Intended Completion Date, the Project Manager shall obtain priced proposals for achieving the CSJM Uessary acceleration from the Contractor..."

Clause No. 31: Early Warning.

"...the Contractor shall warn the Project Manager at the earliest opportunity of specific likely future events or circumstances that may adversely affect the quality of the work, increase the Contract Price, or delay the execution of the Works..."

Clause No. 37: Changes in the Contract Price.

"...if the final quantity of the work done differs from the quantity in the Bill of Quantities for the particular item by more than 25 percent, provided the change exceeds 2 percent of the Initial Contract Price, the Project Manager shall adjust the rate to allow for the change..."

Clause No. 38: Variations.

"...the Contractor shall provide the Project Manager with a quotation for carrying out the Variation when requested to do so by the Project Manager..."

Clause No. 45: Price Adjustment.

"...prices shall be adjusted for fluctuations in the cost of inputs only if provided for in the SCC. If so provided, the amounts certified in each payment certificate, before deducting for Advance Payment, shall be adjusted by applying the respective price adjustment factor to the payment amounts due..." (PPMO, 2010).

Conclusion

Time, Cost and Quality are three sides of a project performance triangle. Project is one time unique process with specific objective which is source of innovation and development. Construction industry has been emerged as an important part of development sector of Nepal as almost all of the infrastructure development projects solely rely on construction activities. Construction industry has provided employment for a lot of labor. It uses lots of construction materials & equipment and hence substantial amount of cash flow. Which in turn increases economic activities and supports for economic development of the nation? Delay has been considered as a common problem in construction industry of Nepal, mostly because of the underlying uncertainties and political liquidity. Time and cost overrun, which are in fact the most important effects of delay, are very common disease in the construction sector of Nepal. Time and cost overrun along with quality has affected almost all running development projects weather the projects are large or small in scale. The review shows time over run and cost overrun is a big issue and it needs serious attention especially for infrastructure projects as most of the tax payer's amount found to be invested in

infrastructure projects. Projects of national priority are under construction phase which need more attention for maintaining time and cost performance. A project has time, cost and quality constraints to be maintained. So, a research considering time, cost and quality should be conducted in every field of construction to develop empirical relation between time, cost and quality. Time extension is not an exception but norms for infrastructure projects should be verified through ecological testing and possible measures should be strongly enforced for systematic performance improvements of projects.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deepest thanks to all the helping hands without which this work would not have been completed. This research is dedicated to all the faculty of Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur, India from engineering and management department. Assoc. Prof. Dr. N.K. Shing and Prof. Dr. Kameshwor Mishra who has enlighten me complete the review paper. I can't forget contribution of Prof. Mukesh Sir and Prof. J.V. Sir, Pro. N. Gupta contribution through continuous support.

References

1. Adenuga OA. Factors Affecting Quality in the Delivery of Public Housing Projects in Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology* 2013; 3.
2. Adenuga OA., n.d.
3. Enshassi A. S. M. S. A. Factors Affecting the Performance of Construction Projects in the Gaza Strip. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Management* 2009; 15: 269-280.
4. Ahmed S, Azher S, Castillo M et al. Construction delays in Florida; an empirical study. [Online] Available at: <www.cm.fiu.edu/pdfs/Research_Reports/Delays_Project.pdf>
5. Aibinu AA, Jagboro GO. The effects of construction delays on project delivery in Nigerian construction industry. *International Journal of Project Management* 2002; 20: 593-599.
6. Alexander TY. *Assessment of Cost and Time Impacts of Public Sector Construction Projects in Ghana*. MBA. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology. 2011.
7. Alfred L. *Construction Productivity*. New York: MC Graw Hill. Anon., n.d. 1998.
8. Ameh OJ, Osegbo EE. Study of relationship between time overrun and productivity on construction sites. *International Journal of Construction Supply Chain Management* 2011; 1(1): 56-67.
9. Apolot R, Alinaitwe H, Tindiwensi D. An Investigation into the Causes of Delay and Cost Overrun in Uganda's Public Sector Construction Projects. *Second International Conference on Advances in Engineering and Technology*. [Online] Available at: <www.mak.ac.ug/documents/Makfiles/aet2011/Apolot.pdf>

- [Accessed 17 March, 2014]
10. Arcila SG. Avoiding Cost Overruns in Construction Projects in the United Kingdom. M Sc. The University of Warwick. 2012.
 11. Arditi D. A. G. M. Total quality management in th construction process. 1998.
 12. Assaf SA, Al-Hejji S. Causes of delay in large construction projects. *International journal of project management*. 2006; 24(4): 349-357.
 13. *Assessment (ESSA, s.l.: s.n)*.
 14. Available at: www.dolidar.gov.np
 15. Available at: www.dolidar.gov.np
 16. Available at: www.dor.gov.np
 17. Azhar N, Farooqi RU. Cost Overrun Factors In Construction Industry of Pakistan. First International Conference on Construction in Developing Countries (ICCIDC-I). *Advancing and Integrating Construction Education, Research & Practice*. Karachi, Pakistan. 2008.
 18. Baker RD. *Time and Cost Correlation in Construction*. 1991.
 19. Bank W. Bridge Development Program: Environment and Social Systems. 2012.
 20. Bromilow FJ, Hinds MF, Moody NF. Australian Institute of Quantity Surveyors: survey of building contract time performance. *The Building Economist* 1980; 79-82.
 21. Bromilow FJ. Measurement and Scheduling of Construction Time and Cost Performance in the Building Industry. *The Chartered Builder* 1974; 10(9): 57-65.
 22. Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS). Major Highlights of Census 2011. [Online] Kathmandu: CBS. Available at: <<http://cbs.gov.np/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/Major-Finding.pdf>> [Accessed 3 August 2013]
 23. Chan DWM, Kumaraswamy MM. Compressing Construction Durations: Lessons Learned from Hong Kong Building Projects. *Internation Journal of Project Management* 2002; 20 (2002): PP 23-35
 24. Choudhury I, Rajan SS. Time - Cost Repationship for Residential Construction in Texas. [Online] Available at: <<https://www.cs.auckland.ac.nz/research/conferences/w78/.../W78-24.pdf>> [Accessed at 25 July, 2014]
 25. Congress TIR. *Guidelins on Quality Systems for Road Bridges*. New Delhi, s.n. DoLIDAR, 2012. *Annual Progress Report*, Kathmandu: s.n. 1998.
 26. Department of Roads (DoR). *Nepal Bridge Standards-2067*. Kathmandu: DoR. 2010.
 27. Department of Roads (DoR). *Road Projects*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.dor.gov.np/road_projects.php> [Accessed 13 May 2014]
 28. DoLIDAR. *Yearly Progress Report for FY: 2070/71*. Kathmandu, Nepal: Department of Local Infrastructure Development and Agricultural Roads DoLIDAR, n.d. [Online]. 2014.
 29. DOR M. *Standard Specification for Road and Bridge works*. s.l., s.n. DOR, n.d. [Online]. 2014.
 30. Durdyev S, Ismail S, Bakar NA. Factors Causing Cost Overruns in Construction of Residential Projects; Case Study of Turkey. *International Journal of Science and Management* 2012; 1(1): 3-12.
 31. Ekantipur, n.d. *80-metre under-construction bridge collapses in Kabilas*. [Online] Available at: <http://kathmandupost.ekantipur.com/printedition/news/2014-05-26/80-metre-under-construction-bridge-collapses-in-kabilas.html>
 32. Facility AI. *Construction Quality Assurance/Quality Control Plan - Groundwater Source Control Measure*, Portland, Oregon: s.n. 2011.
 33. FIDIC. Conditions of Contract for Construction, For Building and Engineering Works Designed By the Employer (Multilateral Development Bank Harmonized Edition). Geneva, Switzerland: International Federation of Consulting Engineers (FIDIC). 2010.
 34. Flyvbjerg B, Holm MKS, Buhl SL. What Causes Cost Overrun in Transport Infrastructure Projects? [Online] Available at: <<http://flyvbjerg.plan.aau.dk/COSTCAUSESASPUBLISHED.pdf>> [Accessed 14 Sep 2014]
 35. GoN, 2063. *Public Procurement Act*. s.l., s.n.
 36. GoN, 2064. *Public Procurement Regulation*. s.l., s.n. HMG/Nepal, 2002. *Public Work Directives*. s.l., s.n.
 37. Haseeb M, Lu X, Bibi A et al. *Causes and Effects of Delays in Large Construction Projects of Pakistan*. [Online] Available at: <[http://www.arabianjbmr.com/VOL_1_\(4\)_KD.php](http://www.arabianjbmr.com/VOL_1_(4)_KD.php)> [Accessed: 5 September 2013]
 38. *International Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 3: 65.
 39. *Internentional Journal of Project Management*, Volume 15, pp. 235-243.
 40. IYER, KNJ. &. KC. *Critical Factors Affecting Quality*. 2006.
 41. Joshi U. D., 2003. *Management Issues in the Early Stages of a Project that lead to Delay in Implementation: A Case Study of Melamchi Water Supply Project*. M Sc. Pokhara University.
 42. Justin Fischgrund, V. O., 2014. *Quality in Construction: Identifying the Gaps*.
 43. Kanji, G. &. W. A., 1998. *Quality Culture in Construction Industry*. s.l.:s.n. Kanji, G. &. W. A., 1998. *Quality Management in Construction Industry*. s.l.:s.n. Kothari, 2004. *Research Methodology*, s.l.: New Age International.
 44. Kikwasi G. J., 2012. *Causes and effects of delays and disruptions in construction projects in Tanzania*. [Online] Available at: <<http://epress.lib.uts.edu.au/journals/index.php/AJCEB-Conference-Series/article/view/3166>> [Accessed: 5 September 2013].
 45. Kothari C. R. and Garg G., 2014. *Research Methodology - Methods and Techniques*. Third Edition. New Delhi,

- India: New Age International (P) Limited.
46. Kothari C. R., 2004. *Research Methodology - Methods and Techniques*. Second Edition. New Delhi, India: New Age International (P) Limited.
 47. LRBP Nepal, n.d. [Online] Available at: www.lrbpnepal.org [Accessed 21 June 2016].
 48. Mahamid I. and Amund B., 2012. Cost deviation in road construction projects: the case of Palestine. *Australasian Journal of Construction Economics and Building*. Vol. 12 (1). PP 58-71
 49. Mahamid I., 2013. Frequency of time overrun causes in road construction in Palestine: Contractors' View. *Organization, Technology and Management in Construction: an International Journal*. Vol. 5 (1). PP720-729.
 50. Mak M. Y., Ng S. T., Chen S. E. and Varnam M., 2000. The relationship between economic indicators and Bromilow's time-cost model: a pilot study. *16th Annual ARCOM Conference, Association of Researchers in Construction Management*. 6-8 September 2000, Glasgow Caledonian University, Akintoye, Vol. 2, PP 587-95.
 51. Mears, P., 1995. *Quality Improvement Tools and Technique*. New York: McGraw Hill. Nepal, G. o., 2067. *Nepal Bridge Standards*. s.l., s.n.
 52. Melamchi Water Supply Project (MWSP), 2014. *Project Progress Report*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.melamchiwater.org/status/progress-report.php> [Accessed 25 February 2014]
 53. Memon AH, Rahman IA, Abdullah MR et al. 2010. *Effects of Construction delay in Large Construction projects: Project Management Consultants Perception*. [Online] Available at http://www.academia.edu/2487617/Proceeding_of_CoGIS2010_Conference_on_Postgraduates_IncentiveResearch_Grant [Accessed: 5 September 2013]
 54. Memon AH, Rahman IA, Abdullah MR et al. Factors Affecting Construction Cost Performance in Project Management Projects: Case of MARA Large Projects. 2011.
 55. Memon AH, Rahman IA, Abdullah MR et al. Time and Cost Performance in Construction Projects in Southern and Central Regions of Peninsular Malaysia. *International Journal of Advances in Applied Sciences (IJAAAS)*. 2012; 1(1): 45-52.
 56. Ministry of Agricultural Development (MoAD), 2013. *Welcome to Ministry of Agricultural Development*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.moad.gov.np/> [Accessed 6 August 2013]
 57. Nega F., 2008. *Causes and Effects of Cost Overrun on Public Building Projects in Ethiopia*. M. Sc. Thesis, Addis Ababa University.
 58. Nepal Electricity Authority (NEA), 2013. *A Year in Review: Fiscal Year 2012/13*. Kathmandu: NEA
 59. Nyabwari, N. E., 2012. *An Investigation on the Causes and Effects of Cost Overrun on Civil Works Projects in Mombasa County*. MBA Thesis, Kenyatta University.
 60. Oakland, J. a. A. A., 1995. Quality management in civil and structural engineering consulting. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*.
 61. Odabasi, E., 2009. *Models for Estimating Construction Duration: An Application for Selected Buildings on the METU Campus*. M. Sc. Thesis, Middle East Technical University.
 62. Olusegun A. Abandonment of construction projects in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Science* 2011; 2: 142-145.
 63. Performance in Construction Projects. s.l.:s.n.
 64. PPA, 2007. *Public Procurement Act*. Kathmandu, Nepal: Nepal Law Commission. 2007.
 65. PPMO. Standard Bid Document for Procurement of Works for above 6 Million Rupees (NCB). [Online] Available at: ppmo.gov.np/leftmenu_page.php?menu_id=34 Accessed 11 April, 2014]
 66. PPR, 2007. *Public Procurement Rules - 2007*. Kathmandu, Nepal: Nepal Law Commission. Project. 2007.
 67. Quality Culture in the Construction Industry.
 68. Regmee P. Quality Control Measures Adopted by Supervision Consultant of Road. 2010.
 69. RRRSDP. *About the Project*. 2010. [Online] Available at: <http://rrr.gov.np/about-project-intro-description.php> [Accessed 1 March 2013]
 70. Salunkhe AA, Patil RS. Effect of Construction Delays on Project Time Overrun: Indian Scenario. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*. 2014. [Online] Available at: <http://www.ijret.org> [Accessed 12 June 2014]
 71. Sambasivan M, Soon YW. Causes and Effects of Delays in Malaysian Construction Industry. *International Journal of Project Management* 2006. [Online] Available at: <http://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/IEL/article/view/4275/4344>
 72. Shr JF, Chen WT. Functional Model of Cost and Time for Highway Construction Projects. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology* 2006; 14(3): 127-138.
 73. Singh R., 2009. *Cost and Time Overruns in Infrastructure Projects: Extent, Causes and Remedies*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.econdse.org/faculty/ram/ram.htm> [Accessed 15 July, 2014]
 74. Singh YK. *Fundamentals of Research Methodology and Statistics*. New Delhi, India: New Age International (P) Ltd. 2009.
 75. Sthapit A. B., Gautam H., Joshi P. R. and Dangol P. M., 2010. *Statistical Methods*. Fifth Edition. Kathmandu, Nepal: Buddha Academic Publishers and Distributors Pvt. Ltd.
 76. Tumi, S. A. H., Omran, A. and Pakir, A. H. K., 2009. Causes of Delays in Construction Industry in Libya. *The International Conference on Economics and*

Administration, Faculty of Administration and Business, University of Bucharest. Bucharest, Romania. 14-15th November 2009.

77. Vidalis S. M. and Najafi F. T., 2002. *Cost and Time Overruns in Highway Construction. Canada, June 2002.* Montreal: Canadian Society for Civil Engineers.
78. Wan Yusoff Wan Mahmood, A. H. M. M. S. M. Z. M. Y. A. B., 2006. Development of
79. Willar D. Improving quality management system implementation in Indonesian construction companies. 2012.